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Research Article

**UNLOCKING THE BEAUTY POTENTIAL OF BUTTERFLY
PEA: EFFICACY, TRENDS, AND INNOVATIONS****Heera Gurusamy^{1*}, Maha Sakthi Athiyannan², Nandhini Thangavel¹,
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Saravanakumar Arthanari².**^{1*}Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Vellalar College of Pharmacy, The Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Erode, India.²Department of Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Vellalar College of Pharmacy, The Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Erode, India.**Abstract:**

Clitoria ternatea, commonly known as butterfly pea or blue pea, is a tropical perennial herb from the Fabaceae family, native to Southeast Asia and India known for its striking blue flowers, the plant has a rich history in Ayurveda and is gaining popularity in the cosmetic industry for its multifunctional benefits. Its extracts are celebrated for their anti-aging and soothing properties, improving skin hydration and enhancing complexion. In hair care, *Clitoria ternatea* provides a natural, chemical-free alternative to synthetic dyes, while also promoting hair growth. Its antimicrobial qualities make it a valuable ingredient in oral care products like mouthwashes and toothpaste, helping reduce plaque, combat bad breath, and support gum health. This versatile plant is now featured in a range of commercial products, including face washes, body lotions, shampoos, and natural hair dyes. Its traditional applications continue to thrive, with homemade remedies like flower-infused oils and teas offering various health benefits. *Clitoria ternatea*'s growing role in cosmetics underscores its sustainability and effectiveness, aligning with the rising demand for eco-friendly and multifunctional ingredients in beauty and personal care products. This review highlights its transformative impact on the natural cosmetics industry.

Keywords: *Clitoria ternatea*, Skin care, Hair care, Oral care, Home-made remedies, Marketed formulation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cosmetics have become a part of many tales in human history¹. As cosmetics have evolved across human history, their origins have become never-ending story. In the prehistoric era around 3000 BC, humans utilized colours for adornment to lure the creatures they intended to hunt. He also managed to avoid enemy attacks by painting his skin and adorning his body, which not only helped him blend in but also frightened his opponents. Cosmetics have a history associated with superstition, religion, combat, and hunting. Later, they were related to medicine².

The ancient man possessed the secret of attracting people with his look; at that time, there were no facials or fairness products to alter a person's look. Individuals' skin and hair beauty is influenced by their health, lifestyle choices, routine work, surroundings, and hygiene. The science of ayurveda employed a wide variety of herbs and plants to make cosmetics that were intended to be both aesthetically pleasing and environmental factor-resistant. The natural ingredients in the botanicals supply the body with nutrients and other essential minerals without having any adverse effects on humans³.

The Drugs and Cosmetics Act describes Cosmetics are characterized as any substance that is meant to be applied to the human body or any portion of it—by rubbing, pouring, sprinkling, spraying, or otherwise—in order to clean, beautify, enhance attractiveness, or alter appearance⁴.

HERBAL COSMETICS:

The word "herb" was used to refer only to nonwoody vegetation, such as those derived from shrubs and trees. In modern era, "herb" can refer to any portion of a plant, including fruits, seeds, stems, bark, flowers, leaves, stigmas, roots, and non-woody plants. They are also utilized in food, cosmetics, medicine, flavonoids, and perfume⁵. Herbal cosmetics are cosmetic products formulated using components that are safe and legal for use in cosmetic formulations to create a unique blend of advantageous cosmetic qualities derived from one or more herbs⁶.

"Natural cosmetics" is another term for herbal cosmetics. Considering that the herbal medications have no negative side effects, demand for them increases rapidly. Since the early days of civilization, people have been tempted to making an attractive impression on others by their appearance. Ayurvedic cosmetics that actually worked were made with a few herbs and plants and the art of Ayurveopathy. The excellent resources found in Ayurvedic cosmetics,

usually referred to as herbal cosmetics, are still existent in this era⁷.

Cosmetics made using plant materials that have cosmetic properties are known as herbal cosmetics. The moderate effect and non-toxic nature of botanicals have led to a recent increase in their use in cosmetics⁴. There are now more opportunities in the cosmeceutical sector due to the rising demand for natural products³.

CLITORIA TERNATEA:

Fig 1.1: *Clitoria ternatea* flower

Clitoria L. consists of sixty species, the majority of which are located in the equatorial zone, with a few in moderate regions. The evergreen genus *Clitoria* features showy, papilionaceous, resupinate blossoms. It also has an infundibuliform calyx with strong bracteoles, stipules, and stipels, as well as stalked ovaries with a bearded, angular style. The term "butterfly pea" is frequently used in English, but there is no common vernacular term for the genus. The majority of literature publications on this species are about *Clitoria ternatea L.*, which has historically been valued for its economic worth⁸.

The *Clitoria ternatea* plant, sometimes described as butterfly pea plant, is actively used by the local population. *Clitoria ternatea*, an enduring leguminous twiner, is a habitant of tropical Asia and is a member of the Fabaceae and sub-family Papilionaceae. Currently, it has become naturalized in China, India, South and Central America, the East and West Indies, and other countries around the world⁹. Butterfly peas are widely employed in various sectors, including as pesticides, food colouring, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, beauty products and cosmetics¹⁰.

HISTORY:

"Shankhpushpi" has a long history with Ayurveda and is trusted to have laxative, nervine, and brain-tonic properties. Ayurvedic literature defines it as a MEDHYA-RASAYANA. It consists of *Clitoria ternatea* (Papilionaceae), *Convolvulus pluricaulis* (Convolvulaceae), *Conscora decusata* (Gentianaceae), *Evolvulus alsinoides* (Convolvulaceae). This Ayurvedic medication is widely used for its central nervous system activity, particularly for enhancing memory and cognitive abilities. The plant *Clitoria ternatea* is known by its popular Sanskrit name, "SHANKPUSHPI," because of its conch-shell-like blossoms. It is said to be an effective "MEDHYA" (nootropic) medication and consequently used to treat "Masasika Roga" (a medical condition to describe mental illness). Plant extracts of *Clitoria ternatea* have been utilized in MEDHYA-RASAYANA, a revitalizing concoction that cures neurological conditions⁹.

A number of floral species have been investigated in order to assess their curative value and identify the primary chemical substance as a result of the development of the Ayurvedic tradition and its scientific investigation. A pharmacological and toxicological assessment of these assertions, which show some significant healthful benefits of this

conventional medication, has been observed in *Clitoria ternatea*¹¹.

A chronology of the principal investigations and significant discoveries in the study of *Clitoria ternatea* from the 1950s to the present:

Research on *C. ternatea* emerged in the 1950s with the intention of elucidating its active elements, botanical chemicals, and pharmacological characteristics. The unique *C. ternatea* anthocyanins known as "ternatins," that give *C. ternatea* flowers striking blue colour, were initially identified in 1985. Following the isolation and structural characterization of further ternatins decades later, the ternatin biosynthetic pathway was postulated. A 2003 analysis of *C. ternatea* lines with various floral colours shed light on the impact of acylation in determining *C. ternatea* floral color. Together with other secondary substance, *C. ternatea* contains an abundance of these special anthocyanins, which makes the plant a fantastic source of organic additions that can raise the nutritional content and aesthetic value of consumer commodities. Even though a series of modern research have attempted to clarify the dosage-related actions of *C. ternatea*, it is still unclear how much each extract component contributes to any given bioactivity that has been assessed¹².

Fig 1.2: A chronology of the principal investigations and significant discoveries in the study of *Clitoria ternatea* from the 1950s to the present

BIOLOGICAL SOURCE:

Clitoria ternatea (CT), a persistent herbaceous plant belongs Fabaceae family, often referred as butterfly pea or Asian pigeon wings¹².

SYNONYM:

Clitoria tanganicensis Micheli, *Clitoria zanzibarensis* Vatke, *Clitoria albiflora* Mattei, *Clitoria bracteata* Poir., *Clitoria mearnsii* De Wild¹³.

TAXONOMICAL CLASSIFICATION:¹⁴⁻¹⁶Table 1.1: Taxonomical classification of *Clitoria ternatea*

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Viridaeplanta
Infrakingdom	Streptophyta
Division	Tracheophyta
Subdivision	Spermatophytina
Infrodivision	Angiospermae
Class	Magnoliopsida
Superorder	Rosanae
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Subfamily	Papilionoideae
Genus	<i>Clitoria</i> L.
Species	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> .

VERNACULAR NAMES:¹⁷Table 1.2: different vernacular names of *Clitoria ternatea*

LANGUAGE	VERNACULAR NAMES
Sanskrit	Shwetanama, Vishnu-Kranta, Ashwakhura, Mohanasini Vishadoshaghni, Ardrakarni, Girikarnika, Ashphota, Aparajita Saukarnika, and Supuspi.
Gujarath	Bismar, Koyala, Garani.
Hindi, Bengali, and Oriya	Aparajit, Aparajita.
Kannada	Billisaiuga, Satugadagida.
Punjab	Dhanattar.
Rajasthan	Koyalri, Titlimatar
Telugu	Sankhupuvvu, Dintana, Gilarnika, and Neela-ghentana.
Tamil	Kuruvilai, Kakkanam, Kakatan, and Kavachi.
English	Pigeon wings, butterfly pea.

BOTANICAL DESCRIPTION:

Clitoria ternatea is a twining vine with nodules and a branched tap root system. The stem of *Clitoria ternatea* are aerial, weak, and twiner. The leaves exhibit reticulate venation and are complex, alternating, and stipulate in nature. It has stipellate leaflets. Stipels and petiolate are pulverized. The inflorescence is axillary and single. Flowers are

bracteate and bracteolate. Bracteoles are often big, pedicellate, heterochlamydeous, complete, bisexual, pentamerous, zygomorphic, and hypogynous. An androecium has ten stamens, among them nine are fused into a cluster and the tenth stamen is free. The calyx possesses five green, synsepalous sepals which show valvate aestivation; the peculiar sepal faces forward.

Fig 1.3: *Clitoria ternatea* plant

The corolla is irregularly papilionaceous, with five petals that are either white or blue in color and show downward imbricate aestivation. This arrangement is known as diadelphous (9) +1. Anthers are dithecized, basifixed, introrse, and dehiscent by means of long slits¹⁷.

MICROSCOPIC CHARACTERS:

Leaf:

Clitoria ternatea Linn leaf transverse section exhibits covering trichomes on both surfaces. The cells forming both the upper and lower epidermis are encased by a single layer of cells that are heavily coated with a thick cuticle. Following the layers of epidermis, there are collenchymatous cells. Polygonal tabular cells make up the upper epidermis, which is followed by a layer of palisade cells. The spongy mesophyll is observed by the sporadically scattered cells in three to five layers. The parenchyma cells contain calcium oxalate crystals. A single layer of border parenchyma, also known as the bundle sheath, covers the vascular bundle and contains lignified xylem vessels¹⁸.

Stem:

TS of stem is almost spherical in shape with a wave-like margin. The cuticle's outermost layer is comprised of simple, glandular trichomes. The endodermis lies between the four layers of the parenchymatous cortical space. Narrow patches are home to pericyclic fibres. While the xylem region is narrow and has more narrow lumen vessels, the phloem region is comparatively narrow¹⁹.

Root:

A transverse section of the root reveals 10 to 20 or more layers of exfoliating cork cells, which are rectangular, thin-walled, and elongated tangentially. The secondary cortex consists of 10–12 layers of large, polygonal, thin-walled cells densely filled with starch grains. A few cells in this region have prismatic calcium oxalate crystals; the lower half of the cortex is covered in solitary or clusters of two to ten lignified cortical fibers; standard components form the secondary phloem; Phloem fibres are found in groups of 2 to 8 with a few solitary fibers being found. The secondary xylem is made up of the usual components; the vessels are supplemented with rectangular, surrounded by pits and possess a little, cone-shaped tail on one end. These vessels are largely found in collections of two or three. xylem fibers resembling phloem fibers, a few displaying pits that resemble slits; xylem parenchyma has uneven walls and a medullary 10 rays that are 1-5 cells broad, oblong, and pitted. Simple and complex starch grains with 2-6 components can be found in phloem, xylem parenchyma, and secondary cortex. Single grains with a diameter of 3-13 μ are also observed in these regions²⁰.

Powder:

Microscopy of powders are yellowish brown; contains fiber fragments and also contains basic and complicated starch grains, typically ranging in diameter from 3 to 13 μ , as well as oblong-bordered pit-filled vessels²⁰. When *C. ternatea* entire plant powder is examined under a microscope, it shows surface views of very thin-walled epidermal cells with paracytic stomata, fibers, xylem arteries having spiral thickenings, and clusters of spongy parenchyma²¹.

SUBSTITUTION/ADULTERANT:

In Northern India, Sankhpushpi is the trade name for *Convolvulus microphyllus* Sieb. ex Spreng; however, geographic variability prevents its availability in the South, where *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. is used as a substitute²². The flower *Convolvulus pluricaulis Choisy*, which has a "Conch" or "Shankh"-shaped bloom, is frequently referred to as "Shankhpushpi." *Clitoria ternatea* L. is a botanical species that is considered as its adulterant or substitute due to its identical flowering characteristics²³.

ALLIED SPECIES:²⁴

The genus *Clitoria* and other adjacent genera contain a few closely related or allied species of *Clitoria ternatea*. The following are a few of *Clitoria ternatea*'s allied species:

- *Clitoria Andrei Fantz*
- *Clitoria albi flora Mattei*
- *Clitoria amazonum Benth*
- *Clitoria angustifolia Kunth*
- *Clitoria annua*
- *Clitoria brachystegia Benth.*
- *Clitoria bracteata Poir.*
- *Clitoria brasiliana L.*
- *Clitoria arborea Benth.*
- *Clitoria australis Benth*

GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION:

The plant was first found in tropical Asia and subsequently spread to Africa, Asia, Australia, North America, the Northwestern and South-Central Pacific regions, the Southwestern and Northwestern regions of North America, and Southern America¹⁶. The *Clitoria* genus is a common garden flower that grows naturally in the world's tropical and subtropical zone. It is also an insignificant climber. In humid and subhumid regions of Asia, America, and Africa, as well as in semi-arid tropical Australia, the genus is

now rare. Around 1800 meters above the surface of the sea, it gets started to grow¹⁴.

It is often cultivated as an aesthetic plant in regions with higher temperatures. It reaches as far south as 24° South latitude, or roughly 20° North latitude, in the Salta province of Argentina. It grows in lawns throughout Africa, usually on black earthenware that is occasionally damp and in old cultivations; in Sudan, it is cultivated for fodder or grazing, and in Kenya, it is cultivated in combination with *Chloris gayana*. This plant's variety is found throughout America, spanning from Florida to Texas and from New Jersey to Kentucky and Arkansas. It is frequently seen in places like the Turks and Caicos Islands, Jamaica, and Puerto Rico. It can be found throughout India however it is most prevalent in the Andaman Islands and southern India up to 1,500 meters in altitude¹⁴.

Since the plant is generally acceptable to animal husbandry and adapts easily to a variety of environmental conditions, it is mostly used as a feed. Once indigenous to the island of Ternate in the Molluca archipelago, this species is now widely cultivated for aesthetic, culinary, or therapeutic uses. It often turns out escaping in 15-cm-tall hedges and thickets in India and the Andaman Islands. It can be produced in Punjab, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, and Karnataka as a fodder climber, either by itself or in combination with annual livestock feed grasses²⁰.

COLLECTION AND CULTIVATION:**Soil:**

It can be adapted to a broad variety of soil types, including calcareous soils, having a pH of 5.5-8.9²⁵. Although it grows well in moderately rich soils as well as it is particularly well adapted to heavy clay alkaline soils. Since *Clitoria ternatea* thrives in rich, moist soil, maintaining consistent soil moisture is crucial for its healthy development²⁴. It grows successfully in areas with sustained rains as well as extended droughts⁹. It grows from sandy places like the Kordo Fan in the Sudan to the relatively drought bearing areas of Zambia, and it needs about 400 mm of rainfall per year, though it also grows well under irrigation. *Clitoria ternatea* can withstand brief periods of flooding due to its inherent traits, but it is not resilient to prolonged flooding or waterlogging²⁴. This plant requires mild shade but may also bloom in full sunshine²⁴. It grows best in locations with mild or infrequent frosts, although it needs a temperature of at least 25°C. It has a limited tolerance for frost, however, and thrives in hot summer weather²⁴. Fertilizer is necessary if the soil is infertile, as Phosphorus (P) and

sulfur (S)-rich soil is usually used to cultivate *Clitoria ternatea* ²⁴.

Propagation:

Seeds are used for propagation; to make hand pod collection easier, the plants can be anchored with bamboo or cultivated with support crops. When the dried pod breaks, butterfly peas rapidly reseed themselves and provide an abundance of seeds ²⁵. It grows well after chopping or pasturing in a small amount of time and produce large quantities as well. In northern Australia, the thick breaking clay soils provide an ideal habitat for *Clitoria ternatea* L. Typically, seeds are sown from the start of the wet season to its midpoint. It thrives during the rainy season when it is sparingly grazed ⁹.

Pest and pest control:

Once established, it tolerates weeds quite well. Some weed control may be obtained by mowing the crop, since the legume's subsequent regrowth will eventually overwhelm the weeds. Early growth will require hand weeding or cultivation if a pure stand is needed. For effective control of weeds during establishment, pre-emergence herbicide must be used two to eight weeks before seeding ²⁵.

Harvesting:

Depending on the seasonal circumstances in which it is produced, it includes around 20% hard seed, which develops quickly in warm, humid weather. Cuttings are used to grow the plant from seed after it is carefully picked by hand ²⁴. *Clitoria ternatea* seeds lack germination when exposed to water due to their hard seed coats; however, after six months in storage, 15-20% of the seeds will germinate. In addition, germination and early plant development have been enhanced by the application of warm water, sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), potassium hydroxide, and dipping in a 100 mg/L solution of sodium cyanide (NaCN). Mechanical scarification boosted the sprouting of 6-month-old seed from 30% to 71% ²⁴.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS: ^{9,14,16,24,26-29}

Clitoria ternatea has been recognized to possess a wide range of plant-based constituents such as tannins, anthocyanins, alkaloids, flavonoids, ternatins, and pentacyclic triterpenoids like taraxerol and taraxerone ²⁶.

Table 1.3: Chemical constituents of *Clitoria ternatea*

Plant parts	Chemical constituents	Uses
Flower	<p>PETALS: Quercetin, myricetin, and kaempferol derivatives include 3-O-(2"-O-alpha-rhamnosyl-6"-O-malonyl)-beta-glucoside and 3-O-(6"-O-alpha-rhamnosyl-6"-O-malonyl) structures, as well as their 3-O-(2",6"-di-O-alpha-rhamnosyl)-beta-glucoside and beta-glucoside variants.</p> <p>FLOWERS: It includes 3-O-beta-glucoside, 3-O-(2"-O-alpha-rhamnosyl-6"-O-malonyl)-beta-glucoside, 3-O-(2"-O-alpha-rhamnosyl)-beta-glucoside, and various delphinidin glycosides such as delphinidin-beta-glucoside. Additionally, it covers eight anthocyanins, including delphinidin-3,5-diglucoside, delphinidin-3-beta-glucoside, malvidin-3-beta-glucoside, kaempferol, p-coumaric acid, as well as preternatins A3 and C4.</p>	<p>protection of the liver, reduction of cell toxicity, larvicidal action, fever reduction, antioxidant properties, anti-diabetic activity, and antibacterial benefits.</p>
Leaves	<p>Alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, glycosides, and reducing sugars. Beta-sitosterol, aparajitin, including 3-rutinoside, 3-neohesperidoside, 3-O-rhamnosyl glycoside, beta-sitosterol, and kaempferol-3-monoglucoside, kaempferol-3-rutinoside, kaempferol-3, I, II, III, and IV kaempferol glycosides</p>	<p>Preventing diabetes mellitus and neurodegenerative disorders. effectively reduces the excessive perspiration. For eruptions, leaf infusion is applied. For earaches, heated leaf juice blended with regular salt is administered</p>

		externally and serves as an antioxidant.
Root	<p>β-carotene, stigmast-4-ene-3,6-diene, 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), along with alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, carbohydrates, proteins, resins, starch, taraxerol, and taraxerone.</p> <p>The root nodule contains various amino acids such as arginine, ornithine, histidine, glycine, alanine, valine, leucine, aminobutyric acid, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, and gamma-aminobutyric acid.</p>	Reducing inflammation of the bladder and urethra, antioxidant, diuretic, and laxative.
Seeds	The nucleoprotein has an amino acid sequence similar to insulin and includes delphinidin-3,3,5-triglucoside, essential amino acids, pentosan, water-soluble mucilage, adenosine, anthoxanthin glucoside, greenish-yellow fixed oil, phenol glycoside, and 3,5,7,4-tetrahydroxy flavone-3-rhamnoglucoside. It also contains a bitter acid resin, tannic acid, 6% ash, ethyl D-galactopyranoside, p-hydroxy cinnamic acid polypeptide, finotin, a highly basic protein, mucilage, and delphinidin 3,3,5-triglucoside. It also contains a greenish-yellow fixed oil and fatty acids, including palmitic, stearic, oleic, linoleic, and linolenic acids.	The seeds are cathartic. Seeds are aperients and purgatives. Seeds are used as a food coloring, for enlarged abdominal viscera, dropsy, and swollen joints.

EXTRACTION PROCESS:

COSMETIC USES:

The cosmetics sector is witnessing a surge in demand for *Clitoria ternatea*, often referred to as butterfly pea flower, due to its many health benefits.

Skin care cosmetic uses:

The skin has to be safeguarded and kept in good condition since it is a tissue that protects the whole body and helps to shield it from environmental factors. The development of wrinkles, scales, dryness, and cracks are indicative of the skin's degeneration process³⁰. Human skin can exhibit a variety of conditions from mild dryness to severe erythema and scaling. A cosmetic formulation that contains only naturally occurring active principles is intended to shield the skin against external or internal hazardous substances³¹. Flowers of the *Clitoria ternatea* L. plant are among those that are extensively used as cosmetics and are believed to offer health advantages³⁰.

1] Anti-oxidant:

The floral extract from *C. ternatea* could be an excellent source of flavonoids, including anthocyanins, that may have medicinal uses. These flavonoids are very good antioxidants, and they may be added to a variety of cosmetic and related products. As a result, these extracts safeguard the skin from becoming dry, wrinkled, scaly, or even from ageing too quickly^{32,33}. The general appearance and texture of the skin are improved by the butterfly pea plant. *Clitoria ternatea*-containing herbal face masks are believed to be a durable and effective method of improving skin tone, making them a good treatment option for hyperpigmentation³⁴.

2] Anti-aging:

Cosmetic lotion containing 5% concentrated butterfly pea flower extract that applied topically can help against premature aging of the skin. This stabilizing process is essential in inhibiting the generation of reactive oxygen species and mitigating the consequences of photoaging³⁵. It is said that consuming the blossoms of *Clitoria ternatea* L. or making herbal tea from their infusion would prevent skin aging and encourage a more youthful complexion. Human keratinocytes have been protected from UV-induced mtDNA damage and H₂O₂-induced cytotoxicity by the flavonol glycosides and acylated anthocyanins, the primary component of the water-soluble extract of *C. ternatea* flowers, may be

employed as a benefit against skin aging³⁶. Butterfly pea flower may be able to prevent fine wrinkles, uneven skin tone and texture, and loss of skin elasticity when applied topically to the skin³⁷.

3] Anti-wrinkle:

Extracts from *C. ternatea* flowers also showed a strong inhibition of elastase and collagenase activities, indicating the flowers can potentially be used as anti-wrinkle agents³⁸.

4] moisture retention and skin complexion:

Butterfly pea flower fermentation solutions are a natural raw material that can be used to create skincare products that have brightening and humidity retention benefits³⁹. The phytochemicals found in *Clitoria ternatea* flowers, such as kaempferol, quercetin glycosides, and ternatin anthocyanins, that enhance skin tone⁴⁰. In cosmetic applications, tea derived from blue pea or butterfly pea blossoms is used to retain the appearance of healthy skin. Research has demonstrated that antioxidants, such as the polyphenols found in butterfly pea plants, may both moisturize skin and shield it from ultraviolet light harm³⁷. Fermentation extract from butterfly pea blossoms is utilized in skincare cosmetics to alleviate skin irritation, redness, and itching. Additionally, it possesses antioxidant properties that aid in moisture retention and offer whitening effects⁴¹.

Advantages:

Synthetic beauty products have the potential to damage skin and result in acne. They could potentially clog your pores and leave your skin feeling either greasy or dry. One doesn't need to worry about them when using natural cosmetics. Because they are natural, one may use them anywhere and at any time without worrying about any side effects. Cosmetic-pharmaceutical products known as "cosmeceuticals" are designed to give particular results, such as sun protection or acne control and anti-wrinkle effects, to strengthen the healthiness and appearance of the skin. Natural cosmetics are suitable for all skin tones, regardless of how dark or pale your complexion is. They work well on all skin types. They are also gentle enough for women with sensitive or oily skin, so they don't need to worry about causing irritation⁷.

Hair care cosmetic uses:

Hair color, style, and maintenance have a big impact on how individuals feel about their bodies and how

they look. An individual's hair communicates their age, gender, sexual orientation, and social standing. The quantity of hair follicles in men and women, as well as in different racial groups, is not significantly different. The kind of hair that each follicle produces, as well as the individual's hair care and cosmetic choices, determine how different each person's hair will appear⁴². Dandruff and hair loss are typical patient complaints that cause a great deal of physical and psychological stress. Hair growth stimulants, conditioners, shampoos, tonics, and antidandruff treatments are all commonly made using natural ingredients. They are sold in the market as herbal formulations⁴³.

The amount of money spent on hair beauty enhancements reflects the attention that is paid to hair look in today's world. On the other hand, hair cosmetics play a crucial role in enhancing patients' adherence to scalp treatments. Preparations meant to be applied to the hair and scalp in order to cleanse, enhance attractiveness, change look, and/or protect with a goal to keep them in excellent condition are known as hair care cosmetics⁴⁴. Flowers of the *Clitoria ternatea* L. plant are among those that are extensively used as cosmetics and are believed to offer health advantages⁴⁵.

1] Hair colouring:

An aqueous extract from butterfly pea blossoms called blue dye has long been used in cosmetics to cover up gray hair. Because natural colorants are safe for skin contact and the public is concerned about the safety of synthetic colorants, natural colorants are much sought after for usage in cosmetics⁴⁶.

2] Hair growth promoter:

Freshly crushed butterfly pea flowers are applied directly to the scalp and eyebrows to color and stimulate hair growth. It's capacity to stimulate hair growth could be connected to its suppression of the activity of the 5α -reductase enzyme³⁹. The phytoconstituents found in *Clitoria ternatea* flowers, such as kaempferol, quercetin glycosides, and ternatin anthocyanins, that stimulate hair growth⁴⁰.

3] Promotes hair health:

In cosmetic applications, tea derived from butterfly pea blossoms is used to preserve the appearance of healthy hair. Another benefit of butterfly peas is its

ability to help maintain a healthy scalp and hair. Moreover, it is a component of hair care cosmetics designed to stop hair loss and graying. According to theory, it improves blood flow to the hair shafts and lowers inflammation, both of which prevent the growth of new hair³⁷.

4] Anti-hairfall:

Shankhpushpi plant, also called *Clitoria ternatea*, is utilized for its therapeutic effects. Because of its rejuvenating qualities, it has been shown to have strong anti-hair fall capabilities and to promote healthy hair development. This plant is utilized in the production of Ayurvedic hair oil, which encourages hair growth and helps prevent hair loss. This herb's paste can be used as a hair mask or ayurvedic hair pack to promote hair growth⁴³.

Oral care cosmical use:

A product or creation proposed to come into contact with teeth in the buccal cavity with the primary or exclusive goal of altering their appearance, cleaning, flavouring, balancing odours, maintaining or maintaining them in a good state of health is referred to as oral cosmetics⁴⁷. Because dental health may affect a person's ability to speak, chew food, and feel confident in themselves, among other aspects of their quality of life, and it is crucial to overall bodily health. Several problems can arise from inadequate dental and oral hygiene. Dental caries and candidiasis are two conditions related to oral health and dentistry. The telang flower is one of the naturally occurring substances that is good for your health (*Clitoria ternatea* L.)⁴⁸.

1] Toothpaste:

Streptococcus mutans is the bacterium responsible for causing caries, a condition that leads to the deterioration of the cementum, dentin, and enamel of teeth. The aqueous extract of *Clitoria ternatea* (telang) flowers is rich in alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and other aromatic compounds, which possess antibacterial properties that inhibit the growth of bacteria and insects⁴⁸. Due to its recognized antibacterial effects, this extract specifically targets the oral bacterium *S. mutans*. The extract from *Clitoria ternatea* flowers has been utilized in the formulation of toothpaste and mouthwash to combat dental cavities and prevent tooth decay⁴⁹.

MARKETED FORMULATION: ⁵⁰⁻⁵⁵Table 1.4: Marketed formulation of *Clitoria ternatea*

Product	Brand name	Company name	prize
LOTION: Blue Butterfly Pea Body Lotion	Earth rituals	Earth rituals	1100.00
BODY WASH: Blue Butterfly Pea Body Wash	Earth rituals	Earth rituals	1200.00
SHAMPOO: Butterfly Pea Hair Cleanser	Coco roots Organic	Coco roots Organic	340.00
FACE WASH: Anti Acne Face Wash - Dewdrop	Light Up Beauty	Bo international pvt. Ltd.,	329.00
Blue pea flower tea	Preserva Wellness	Trigya Health Products Pvt. Ltd.	500.00
<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> Flower Liquid Extract	Purnenso select	Purnenso select	185.00

HOME MADE REMEDIES:**Blue tea:**

Clitoria ternatea L.'s dry petals are used to make blue tea, often referred to known as butterfly pea or blue pea tea. It is prepared by placing the butterfly pea flowers into a cup and add boiling water Allow the water to settle for five minutes, or until it becomes a vivid blue colour. Then add sugar or honey for sweet taste if desired. Also add lime or lemon juice for extra flavour ⁵⁶. Benefits of consuming blue tea as they are rich in antioxidants, aids in regulating blood sugar levels and promotes heart health and also has antibacterial, anti-diabetic, and anti-cancer properties ⁵⁶.

Adverse effects:

Some anecdotal evidence claims that if we consume *Clitoria ternatea* tea in large amount may cause nausea, stomach ache and diarrhoea ⁵⁶. It's generally safe when used in moderation. However, allergies may affect some. Breathing difficulties, oedema, and itching are possible symptoms. Contact your healthcare practitioner if you feel that butterfly pea flowers are causing an allergy in you ⁵⁷. Information regarding drug interactions is scarce. If you take

medicine, before drinking butterfly pea tea, make sure to speak with your physician ⁵⁷. Additional research on its safety for pregnant or nursing mothers are necessary. They should consult healthcare professionals before consuming ⁵⁷.

HOME MADE REMEDIES FOR SKIN CARE:**Butterfly pea flower skin toner:****1] Skin toner-Type-1:**

The key ingredients are Butterfly pea flowers, witch hazel, glycerine. It is prepared by taking a clean glass container and add the butterfly pea flowers and witch hazel. For every half cup of witch hazel, use one pea flower. Take out the pea flowers after allowing the infusion for a full day out of direct sunlight. Add the glycerin thoroughly by shaking or stirring. To preserve from UV light, store it in a dark place. Benefits are that it promotes levels of Collagen and Elastin and also provide Skin Hydration and Skin Irritation Relief. But some precautions are taken before applying to your entire face, apply a patch test on a little spot of skin. Witch hazel has the lowest possible safety rating of Safety Class 1A, according to The Botanical Safety Handbook. However, some people may experience allergic condition those who are Asteraceae family species. Although butterfly pea flowers are thought to be healthy for skin, those who are allergic to species in the Fabaceae family may experience allergic responses ⁵⁸.

2] Skin toner-Type-2:

The major ingredients are 1 cup distilled water and 2-3 butterfly pea flowers. One or two drops of essential oil (rose or lavender) are optional. It is prepared by introducing the butterfly pea flowers into the boiling distilled water. In order to extract the colour and health-promoting components from the flowers, let the mixture boil for 5 to 10 minutes. Take it away the heat source and let it cool down fully. Take out the flowers with a strainer and transfer the infused water to a fresh spray bottle. If desired, add a few drops of essential oil and then shake well before use. It is applied to skin to moisturize and refresh it. It also relieves itching and redness^{59,60}.

3] Add in hot bath:

Powdered butterfly pea flowers are extensively used for thousands of years in Ayurvedic medication to cure a wide range of conditions. It can be used, for example, stir 1-2 spoonsful of butterfly pea flower powder into your bathwater and let it steep for 20 to 30 minutes. Powdered butterfly pea flower reduces stiffness in the body and reduces aching muscles. The advantages of butterfly pea flower can be absorbed through the skin when warm water helps to open the pores.

Butterfly Pea Flower Face Mask:

Powdered butterfly pea flower is an important ingredient in face masks⁶¹. It includes one tablespoon of butterfly pea flower powder and honey. Preparation involves blending a teaspoon of butterfly pea flower powder with a teaspoon of honey until thoroughly mixed. Apply the resulting mixture to your neck and face. After 15 minutes, wash off from the face and neck. It reduces inflammation and enhances skin health due to the flavonoids and antioxidants in the powder⁶¹.

Butterfly pea face pack:

Butterfly pea face pack contains Butterfly pea powder and coconut milk prepared by taking butterfly pea flower powder and coconut milk, mix well and then apply to the face and neck. After 15–20 minutes wash with cold water. It is used to moisturizing the skin. Reduces acne and other skin irritations⁶².

HOMEMADE REMEDIES FOR HAIR CARE:**1] Butterfly pea flower hair oil:**

Coconut oil and dried butterfly pea flower are involved in preparation which is prepared by placing 1/2 cup of dried butterfly pea flowers into a jar with coconut oil. Seal the jar and store it in a dark location for 2-4 weeks. After that strain the flowers from the oil. Now it can be used regularly.

2] Butterfly pea flower hair mask:

Butterfly pea flower powder, and honey are the key ingredients in hair mask prepared by combining one tablespoon of butterfly pea flower powder with raw honey and a well-mashed banana. If necessary, add a

bit of water to achieve the desired consistency. Apply the mixture to clean, damp hair and cover with a suitable cap or wrap with a plastic cap, and leave it on for 30-45 minutes. Rinse thoroughly with water and follow up with shampoo⁶³. They are rich in anthocyanin, that promotes the flow of blood to the scalp to promote hair rejuvenation; Hydrating the skin, reducing dryness and flakes; Prevents grey hair; Prevents hair loss and has Anti-inflammatory effect, reduces itching and irritation; and has antimicrobial qualities to aid in the healing of skin infections⁶³.

CONCLUSION:

Clitoria ternatea stands out as a versatile plant with a rich historical background and broad range of applications. *Clitoria ternatea*, with its rich phytochemical profile, it emerges as active ingredient in the modern cosmetic landscape. Its potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties make it highly effective across various applications, including skincare, haircare, and oral hygiene. The plant's ability to address signs of aging, promote hair growth, prevent graying, and enhance oral health underscores its multifunctional benefits. As consumer interest shifts towards natural, eco-friendly, and multifunctional cosmetics, *Clitoria ternatea* stands out as a promising ingredient that aligns with these trends. The presence of *Clitoria ternatea* in both marketed formulations and homemade remedies illustrates its versatility and growing role in natural and sustainable beauty solutions. The ongoing exploration of *Clitoria ternatea* promises to unlock further benefits and applications, solidifying *Clitoria ternatea's* role as a valuable asset in both traditional and contemporary cosmetic and health solutions.

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